

Orbits on body's shells in the frictionless case without medium and with non constant angular velocity in the homogeneous field

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Contents

1	Development of the basic equations	1
2	Solutions to the differential equations	5
3	The paraboloid	7
4	The ball	8

1 Development of the basic equations

g = gravitational acceleration

$w(t)$ = angular velocity, depending from the time t .

$\vec{x} \in R^3$

$z = h(r)$ is the convex function with continuous second differential (twice continuous differentiable and $h''(r) \geq 0$). This assumption is necessary to avoid

“thrown trajectories of the body”.

$$\vec{x} = \begin{pmatrix} r \cos \varphi \\ r \sin \varphi \\ h(r) \end{pmatrix} \quad \frac{d}{dt} \varphi(t) = w(t)$$

$$h'(r) := \frac{\partial h}{\partial r}(r) \quad h''(r) := \frac{\partial^2 h}{\partial r^2}(r)$$

We calculate the differential to the time:

$$\frac{d\vec{x}}{dt} = \begin{pmatrix} \dot{r} \cos \varphi - r \sin \varphi \cdot \dot{\varphi} \\ \dot{r} \sin \varphi + r \cos \varphi \cdot \dot{\varphi} \\ h'(r) \cdot \dot{r} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{d\vec{x}}{dt} \right)^2 &= (\dot{r} \cos \varphi - r \sin \varphi \cdot \dot{\varphi})^2 + (\dot{r} \sin \varphi + r \cos \varphi \cdot \dot{\varphi})^2 + (h'(r) \cdot \dot{r})^2 \\ &= \dot{r}^2 \cos^2 \varphi - 2r\dot{r} \cos \varphi \sin \varphi \cdot \dot{\varphi} + r^2 \sin^2 \varphi \cdot \dot{\varphi}^2 \\ &\quad + \dot{r}^2 \sin^2 \varphi + 2r\dot{r} \sin \varphi \cos \varphi \cdot \dot{\varphi} + r^2 \cos^2 \varphi \cdot \dot{\varphi}^2 + h'(r)^2 \cdot \dot{r}^2 \end{aligned}$$

With using $\sin^2 \varphi + \cos^2 \varphi = 1$:

$$= \dot{r}^2 + r^2 \dot{\varphi}^2 + h'(r)^2 \cdot \dot{r}^2$$

with that:

$$v^2 = \left(\frac{d\vec{x}}{dt} \right)^2 = \dot{r}^2 \cdot (1 + h'(r)^2) + r^2 \dot{\varphi}^2$$

$$\text{Kinetic energy: } T = \frac{mv^2}{2} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot m \cdot \left(\frac{d\vec{x}}{dt} \right)^2$$

m = mass of the ball on the rotation body's shell

$$\text{potential energy} = V = +gzm = g \cdot h(r) \cdot m$$

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial z} = gm = -F$$

It is a conservative system, see Budo [2] §9.2, p.45 and §29.2, p.139.

Because of the 3 restrictions

$$\vec{x} = \begin{pmatrix} r \cos \varphi \\ r \sin \varphi \\ h(r) \end{pmatrix}$$

there is a **holonomic** system, see Budo [2], §31.2, p.148, 149, equation (4).

The Lagrangian function L is with Budo [2] §34.2 p.163:

$$L = T - V$$

$$L = \frac{1}{2} \cdot m \cdot (\dot{r}^2 \cdot (1 + h'(r)^2) + r^2 \dot{\varphi}^2) - g \cdot h(r) \cdot m$$

The Lagrange equations of the second kind are (see Budo [2], §34.2, p.162,163)

$$\frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{r}} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial r} = 0$$

of conservative holonomic systems.

r is a "general" coordinate, see Budo [2], §34.1, p.162, equation (3).

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial r} = \frac{m}{2} \cdot (\dot{r}^2 \cdot 2h'(r) \cdot h''(r) + 2\dot{\varphi}^2 r) - g \cdot h'(r) \cdot m$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{r}} = \frac{m}{2} \cdot (1 + h'(r)^2) \cdot 2\dot{r}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{r}} = \frac{m}{2} \cdot ((1 + h'(r)^2) \cdot 2\ddot{r} + 2h'(r)h''(r)\dot{r} \cdot 2 \cdot \dot{r})$$

$$= \frac{m}{2} \cdot (2 \cdot (1 + h'(r)^2) \cdot \ddot{r} + 4h'(r)h''(r)\dot{r}^2)$$

with that:

$$0 = \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{r}} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial r}$$

$$= \frac{m}{2} \cdot (2 \cdot (1 + h'(r)^2) \cdot \ddot{r} + 4h'(r)h''(r) \cdot \dot{r}^2)$$

$$- \frac{m}{2} \cdot (2\dot{r}^2 h'(r)h''(r) + 2\dot{\varphi}^2 r) + g \cdot h'(r) \cdot m$$

At last we obtain:

$$0 = (1 + h'(r)^2) \cdot \ddot{r} - w(t)^2 \cdot r + h'(r)h''(r) \cdot \dot{r}^2 + g \cdot h'(r) \quad (1)$$

with $\dot{\varphi} = w$. This is one nonlinear differential equation of second order of $r(t)$.
 $h(t) = h(r(t))$

Transformation of (1) in a differential equation system of first order, see Forster [4], §10, p.99:

$$\dot{r} = a \quad (2)$$

$$0 = (1 + h'(r)^2) \cdot \dot{a} - w(t)^2 \cdot r + h'(r)h''(r)a^2 + g \cdot h'(r)$$

These are 2 differential equations of first order of the searched variables a and r .

special case: r, w constant, with equation (1) we get:

$$0 = g \cdot h'(r) - w^2 \cdot r$$

transformed:

$$w^2 = \frac{g \cdot h'(r)}{r}$$

This is the known formula of the angular velocity in [8] chapter 1. But for the general case it is valid:

$$|\vec{v}| = \sqrt{\dot{r}^2 \cdot (1 + h'(r)^2) + r^2 \cdot w(t)^2}$$

In the case $r = \text{const.}$ follows $v = r \cdot w$ with w constant. To the equation (1) there are perhaps other solutions with non constant r .

The ball's shell:

R is the radius of the ball

$$h(r) = R - \sqrt{R^2 - r^2}$$

$$h'(r) = \frac{r}{\sqrt{R^2 - r^2}} \quad h''(r) = \frac{R^2}{(R^2 - r^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}}$$

With (1) we get an differential equation of the ball:

$$0 = \left(1 + \frac{r^2}{R^2 - r^2}\right) \cdot \ddot{r} - w^2 r + \frac{r R^2 \dot{r}^2}{(R^2 - r^2)^2} + \frac{gr}{\sqrt{R^2 - r^2}} \quad (3)$$

This differential equation can be transformed in two differential equation of first order.

2 Solutions to the differential equations

The equation system (2) can be solved with Kamke [6], §2, 6.3, p.38 with one power series statement. If the angular velocity w is not constant, there is evident no possibility to solve exactly (2) or (1) to a general function $h(r)$.

Now we assume w is **temporal constant**. Then we can transform the differential equation (1) to one differential equation of first order see Kamke [6], §4, 15.3(a), p.68.

$$\begin{aligned}\rho(r) &:= \dot{r}(t(r)) & \dot{r} &\neq 0 \\ \rho'(r) &:= \frac{\partial \rho(r)}{\partial r} = \ddot{r}(t(r)) \cdot \frac{dt(r)}{dr}\end{aligned}$$

Differentiation of the inverse function:

$$= \ddot{r}(t(r)) \cdot \frac{1}{\frac{dr(t)}{dt}} = \frac{\ddot{r}(t(r))}{\frac{dr(t(r))}{dt}} = \frac{\ddot{r}(t(r))}{\rho(r)}$$

It follows:

$$\ddot{r}(t(r)) = \rho'(r) \cdot \rho(r) \quad \text{or} \quad \ddot{r} = \rho \cdot \rho'$$

Because of (1) we obtain with this transformation:

$$0 = (1 + h'(r)^2) \cdot \rho \rho' - w^2 r + h'(r) h''(r) \rho^2 + g \cdot h'(r) \quad (4)$$

We search $\rho(r)$.

After this $\dot{r}(t) = \rho(r)$ must be solved to $r(t)$.

Separation of variables:

$$\frac{dr}{dt} = \rho(r) \quad \Rightarrow \quad t = \int_{r_0}^r \frac{d\bar{r}}{\rho(\bar{r})} + c$$

For example see Forster [4], §11, theorem 1, p.111,112, c is integration constant. Now we treat the differential equation of first order:

$$\rho'(r) = \frac{w^2 r - h'(r) h''(r) \rho^2 - g \cdot h'(r)}{(1 + h'(r)^2) \cdot \rho}$$

Partition:

$$\rho'(r) = k(r) \cdot \frac{1}{\rho} - f(r) \cdot \rho$$

with:

$$\frac{w^2 r - g \cdot h'(r)}{1 + h'(r)^2} := k(r) \quad \frac{h'(r)h''(r)}{1 + h'(r)^2} =: f(r)$$

with that:

$$\rho'(r) + f(r)\rho - k(r) \cdot \frac{1}{\rho} = 0 \quad (5)$$

This is one Bernoulli differential equation with exponent -1, see Kamke [6], §1, 4.5, p.19.

In the form $\rho\rho' = k(r) - f(r)\rho^2$ we can treat this equation as Abel differential equation of second kind (see Kamke [6], §1, 4.11(a), p.26.27), that can perhaps be solved with much effort.

Then in Kamke [6], §1, 4.14, p.29 there is a further method, that can be perhaps used to solve the differential equation.

Now we treat the differential equation as Bernoulli differential equation. ($\alpha = -1$)

$$z(r) = \rho^{1-\alpha}(r) = \rho(r)^2$$
$$\rho = z^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \rho' = \frac{1}{2} \cdot z^{-\frac{1}{2}} \cdot z'$$

Insertion in the Bernoulli differential equation:

$$\frac{1}{2} \cdot z^{-\frac{1}{2}} z' = z^{-\frac{1}{2}} \cdot k(r) - f(r)z^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

We get with:

$$z' = 2 \cdot k(r) - 2 \cdot f(r) \cdot z$$

one linear differential equation

With Forster [4], §11, p.116, theorem 3 it is valid for the solution $z(r)$:

$$z(r) = \varphi(r) \cdot \left(c + \int_{r_0}^r \varphi(\bar{r})^{-1} \cdot 2 \cdot k(\bar{r}) d\bar{r} \right)$$

with

$$\varphi(r) := \exp\left(-\int_{r_0}^r 2 \cdot f(\bar{r}) d\bar{r}\right) \quad \text{and} \quad c = z(r_0)$$

with that:

$$z(r) = \varphi(r) \cdot \left(c + 2 \cdot \int_{r_0}^r \frac{k(\bar{r})}{\varphi(\bar{r})} d\bar{r}\right)$$

We obtain:

$$\rho = z^{\frac{1}{2}} = \left(\varphi(r) \cdot \left(c + 2 \cdot \int_{r_0}^r \frac{k(\bar{r})}{\varphi(\bar{r})} d\bar{r}\right)\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

It is valid see before:

$$t = \int_{r_0}^r \frac{dr}{\rho(r)} + c \quad \text{or} \quad \dot{r}(t) = \rho(r)$$

It follows $t(r)$ or $r(t)$ with that one solution with 3 integrals.

3 The paraboloid

The case of the paraboloid with angular velocity = w non temporal constant can only be treated as the general case $h(r)$. If the angular velocity is temporal constant, then we can simplify the solution of the equation.

$a \in R$ dimension of a is metre⁻¹

$$h(r) = ar^2 \quad h'(r) = 2ar \quad h''(r) = 2a$$

From equation (1) we get:

$$0 = (1 + 4a^2r^2) \cdot \ddot{r} - w^2r + 2ar \cdot 2a \cdot \dot{r}^2 + g \cdot 2ar$$

$$0 = (1 + 4a^2r^2) \cdot \ddot{r} - r \cdot (w^2 - 2ga) + 4r^2a^2\dot{r}$$

We multiply by the integrating factor $\dot{r}$:

$$0 = (1 + 4a^2r^2) \cdot \dot{r}\ddot{r} + 4r^3a^2\dot{r} - \dot{r}r \cdot (w^2 - 2ga)$$

Differentiation of a product and a sum: $w = \text{const.}$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\dot{r}^2}{2} \cdot (1 + 4a^2r^2) - \frac{r^2}{2} \cdot (w^2 - 2ga) \right) = 0$$

It follows:

$$\frac{\dot{r}^2}{2} \cdot (1 + 4a^2 r^2) - \frac{r^2}{2} \cdot (w^2 - 2ga) = c = \text{const.}$$

With $c \in R$ transformed:

$$\dot{r}^2 = \frac{c + \frac{r^2}{2} \cdot (w^2 - 2ga)}{\frac{1}{2} \cdot (1 + 4a^2 r^2)}$$

at last:

$$\frac{dr}{dt} = \sqrt{\frac{2c + r^2 \cdot (w^2 - 2ga)}{1 + 4a^2 r^2}} =: g(r)$$

Separation of the variables for example see Forster [4], §11, theorem 1, p. 111, 112:

$$t = \int_{r_0}^r \frac{d\bar{r}}{g(\bar{r})} + c_1 \quad c_1 = \text{integration constant}$$

$$\Rightarrow \quad t - c_1 = \int_{r_0}^r \sqrt{\frac{1 + 4a^2 \bar{r}^2}{2c + \bar{r}^2 \cdot (w^2 - 2ga)}} d\bar{r}$$

It follows $t(r)$ or $r(t)$.

The advantage is that with constant angular velocity there is only one integral, but this integral must be calculated numerically.

4 The ball

Now we calculate the solution of the ball as far as possible.

$$h(r) = R - \sqrt{R^2 - r^2} \quad h'(r) = \frac{r}{\sqrt{R^2 - r^2}} \quad h''(r) = \frac{R^2}{(R^2 - r^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}}$$

with the general formula of $f(r)$: $w = \text{const.}$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{r_0}^r f(r) d\bar{r} &= \int_{r_0}^r \frac{h'(\bar{r})h''(\bar{r})}{1 + h'(\bar{r})^2} d\bar{r} \\ &= \int_{r_0}^r \frac{\bar{r}R^2 d\bar{r}}{(R^2 - \bar{r}^2)^2 \cdot \left(1 + \frac{\bar{r}^2}{R^2 - \bar{r}^2}\right)} = \int_{r_0}^r \frac{\bar{r}R^2 d\bar{r}}{(R^2 - \bar{r}^2) \cdot (R^2 - \bar{r}^2 + \bar{r}^2)} \end{aligned}$$

For example see Gröbner [5], section 15, p.17, Nr. 21g:

$$\int_{r_0}^r f(\bar{r}) d\bar{r} = \int_{r_0}^r \frac{\bar{r}}{R^2 - \bar{r}^2} d\bar{r} = \left[-\frac{1}{2} \cdot \ln(R^2 - \bar{r}^2) \right]_{r_0}^r$$

With that it follows:

$$\varphi(r) = \exp \left(-2 \cdot \int_{r_0}^r f(r) d\bar{r} \right) = (R^2 - r^2) \cdot c_2$$

c_2 = integration constant

$$\begin{aligned} k(r) &= \frac{w^2 r - g \cdot h'(r)}{1 + h'(r)^2} = \frac{w^2 r - \frac{gr}{\sqrt{R^2 - r^2}}}{1 + \frac{r^2}{R^2 - r^2}} \\ &= \frac{\left(\frac{w^2 r \cdot \sqrt{R^2 - r^2} - gr}{\sqrt{R^2 - r^2}} \right)}{\left(\frac{R^2 - r^2}{R^2 - r^2} \right)} = \frac{w^2 r \cdot \sqrt{R^2 - r^2} - gr}{R^2} \cdot \sqrt{R^2 - r^2} \\ &= \frac{r}{R^2} \cdot ((R^2 - r^2) \cdot w^2 - g \cdot \sqrt{R^2 - r^2}) \end{aligned}$$

We calculate:

$$\frac{k(r)}{\varphi(r)} = \frac{\frac{r}{R^2} \cdot ((R^2 - r^2) \cdot w^2 - g \cdot \sqrt{R^2 - r^2})}{c_2 \cdot (R^2 - r^2)} = \frac{1}{c_2} \cdot \left(\frac{rw^2}{R^2} - \frac{g}{R^2} \cdot \frac{r}{\sqrt{R^2 - r^2}} \right)$$

Integration see for example Gröbner [5], section 236, p.51, Nr. 5b:

$$\int_{r_0}^r \frac{k(\bar{r})}{\varphi(\bar{r})} d\bar{r} = \frac{1}{c_2} \cdot \left[\frac{w^2 \bar{r}^2}{2R^2} + \frac{g}{R^2} \cdot \sqrt{R^2 - \bar{r}^2} \right]_{r_0}^r$$

At last we obtain as solution:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(r) &= \left(\varphi(r) \cdot \left(c + 2 \cdot \int_{r_0}^r \frac{k(\bar{r})}{\varphi(\bar{r})} d\bar{r} \right) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ t &= \int_{r_0}^r \frac{d\bar{r}}{\rho(\bar{r})} + c \end{aligned}$$

From the solution with 3 integrals we get one solution with one integral. But this integral must be determined numerically.

In the case of non constant angular velocity we can treat the ball only as the general case.

We get with the solution $r(t)$ because of $\gamma = \arcsin \frac{r(t)}{R}$ the temporal height angle function.

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